

OUR FAVORITE WAYS TO TEACH FAIRY TALES

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Abstract: A fairy tale is a genre belonging to the epic type of folklore, which encourages the reader to do good and draw the correct conclusions from the events. Teaching samples of this genre to students of school age contributes to their intellectual and spiritual education. Below we will talk about the methods of teaching and teaching the fairy tale genre to students during the lessons.

Key words: good attracts, magical world, character, phrases, drama class

One of the reasons why the fairy tale genre is well received and read with interest by children in folk oral creativity is the impressiveness, sharpness, meaningfulness of the fairy tale language and its closeness to the folk language. In most fairy tales, the image of real life is interspersed with adventure elements.

The acute interesting plot of the fairy tale, the extraordinary wonderful situation in the development of the story captivates children, the valor in it, the strong, resourceful, brave, agile heroes, the ideological direction of the fairy tale, in which the power of goodness – the constant triumph of good attracts children. The form of storytelling adopted in the fairy tale is the repeated repetition of the same words and phrases, tonality, impressiveness of the language, vitality of the means of expression, great fun for children. The participants in the fairy tale are often merciful, generous, fair and evil, miserable, greedy characters who are their opposite.

The pedagogical value of the fairy tale is that readers rejoice in the fact that correctness, honesty have won in it, that the poor are saved from hardship, that is, good, goodness have come true, and evil, evil have been condemned. They want it to always be the same in life. For example, in the fairy tale "honesty" (3rd grade), the main idea was to help the poor, to live a life of his own labor, and even the idea that this is the desire of the whole people was put forward, while in the fairy tale "the punishment of the cunning man" (4th grade) the idea was put forward that the correctness of Both tales end with a triumph of honesty.

When working on a fairy tale, it is important not only to read a fairy tale, but also to teach it to tell. Telling a fairy tale will grow oral speech, enrich children's speech with new words and phrases.

Enchant your students by exploring the magical world of fairy tales—and teach the difference between right and wrong, good and evil, and much more.

In addition to being enthralling stories, fairy tales have been teaching children important morals and life lessons for centuries. For example, "Little Red Riding Hood" demonstrates the importance of being careful who you trust, while the lesson learned from "The Three Little Pigs" is that putting in the hard work from the beginning rather than taking a shortcut - will eventually pay off.

Bringing fairy tales into your classroom is a great way to spark your students' imaginations while simultaneously teaching them about culture, history, and, of course, the art of storytelling—conventions such as narrative structure, themes, and archetypes.

Use fairy tales to teach the judicial process by putting characters on trial. For example, Jack from "Jack and the Beanstalk" is a great character to place under examination. Discuss the following questions with the class:

What crimes did Jack commit? (Theft, trespassing, etc.)

What proof is there that he committed the crimes?

Are there any witnesses? What might they say if asked to give evidence?

Divide the class into groups, with one group acting as the prosecution, one as the defense, and one as the jury (you could even add a judge, witnesses, and detectives), and then act out a mock trial in the classroom.

Children's literature helps a young child make sense of what it is to be human and helps them understand the world around them. The fairy tale genre provides ways for children to receive important messages. Although there are some themes in fairy tales that are unrealistic, the overall effect is positive and offers fundamental elements for children's development. Based on the Jungian interpretation, fairy tales teach children how to deal with basic human conflicts, desires, and relationships in a healthy way; acquiring these skills can ultimately impact a child's health, quality of life, or even influence its values and beliefs in the future. The Jungian interpretation, developed by psychotherapist Carl Jung, is a symbolic approach that creates a dialectical relationship between consciousness and the unconscious. Those who use the Jungian interpretation do not perceive therapy as a typical client-therapist relationship where in the client is treated, but rather perceive themselves as guides to help another person delve into the unconscious. Jungian therapy, also called analytical psychotherapy, treats essentially all unconscious sources such as dreams, fantasies, daydreams, even paintings and drawings.

Taking into account all the above points, the construction of fairy tale lessons can be as follows:

1. Introducing the fairy tale:

- a) preparing students to understand the fairy tale;
- b) the teacher's expressive reading of a fairy tale, retelling, etc.

2. Conducting a short conversation in order to determine to what extent the students perceived the fairy tale;

3. Read and analyze the fairy tale in parts; some visual aids in it, finding synonyms, dictionary work (explaining the meaning of some words);

4. Preparing to tell a story (reading inside);

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It is necessary to work on Proverbs presented in fairy tales, to convey the ideas that are being put forward in them to the children's minds, to grow a connected speech by memorization, to increase the effectiveness of speech. For example, in the fairy tale "The Honest boy" (1st grade), the story is told that the boy, by his truthfulness, was pleasing to the King. And the conclusion corresponding to the idea of a fairy tale is expressed in the proverb "Speak

correctly, even if a sword comes to your head." When readers understand the content of this proverb, They themselves can compose a fairy tale and tell a story, as above.

After reading the fairy tale and introducing it to its content, readers are asked, opposite, the meaning of the words juice, good deed, khivchin, muhaiyo. Answers are completed, summarized.

In the process of working with the text of a fairy tale, it is also important to work on the artistic means used in it: revitalization, metaphors, exaggerations.

What do we call it when an author takes a classic fairy tale and changes it into something completely different? A fractured fairy tale. Kids love them. "It's by far my students' favorite language arts unit every year," writes teacher Jessie Averson, a second-grade teacher in Tennessee. We asked teachers across the country for their fractured-fairy-tale lesson plans. Here are the top 11 ideas. (Plus, fractured-fairy-tale book lists at the bottom of the page!)

1. Define fairy tales

"Start off by asking students to share their favorite fairy tales. Record the list on a piece of chart paper. Then ask the class: 'What makes a fairy tale a fairy tale?' You'll be amazed at their answers, and it will lay the groundwork for all the work that follows." - Jessie Averson

2. Tell a tale

"Choose a fairy tale that you know well and TELL the story - no props, no pictures - just tell it. Storytelling is becoming a lost art. You will be amazed at how your students respond as they paint pictures in their minds while listening to your words. My students become instantly quiet and focused when I begin to tell a story." - Linda Joyce

3. Collaborate

"Read three or four or five traditional fairy tales aloud. If your students are familiar enough with the stories, tell the stories collaboratively as a class at circle time. As they relate the tale together, your students may discover that they do not all remember the story the same way." - Ellen Ivory

4. Readers theater

"Readers theater is essential. Choose a fairy tale or two and have groups of three or four students each take a different version and perform it as readers theater! My second graders loved it and they made their own props too!" - Mallory Wintercorn

5. Point of view

"Fractured fairy tales are great for teaching about point of view. Read titles such as 'Believe Me, Goldilocks Rocks!' or 'The Story of the Three Bears as Told by Baby Bear' by Nancy Jean Loewen and talk about how different characters might have a different perspective. Loewen also has versions of 'Cinderella' and 'The Three Little Pigs.'" - Karen Griffin

6. Pull STEM into your fairy-tale lesson plans

"As a side STEM activity for The Three Little Pigs, gather building materials such as straws, Popsicle sticks, LEGO, etc., and explore how effective they are as building materials!" - April JW

7. Go cross-curricular

"We make our fairy-tale unit cross-curricular. We plant beans after reading 'Jack and the Beanstalk.' We also build castles with recyclable items. After reading 'Cinderella,' we do an activity where we measure Cinderella's, her sisters' and her godmother's shoes. We do problem-solving with the characters from fairy tales. It all ends with Fairy Tale Day, when

kids dress up as princesses, knights, and dragons. Such a fun celebration for everyone!" - Mylene Arseneau

8. Rewrite the story

"I like the idea of a creative writing assignment or—for younger kids—a storytelling assignment. Swap the bad guys in the stories. The Big Bad Wolf from Little Red Riding Hood chases Hansel and Gretel. What would happen? How would the stories be different?" - Phil Weber

9. Improv

"In drama class, I would choose a fairy tale and then change three objects in the story and the students would have to come up with ways to keep the storyline but still include the objects. For Snow White, instead of an apple, use a tissue box; instead of a mirror, use a computer. The kids loved it!" - Laurie Elliot

10. Travel the world

"There are so many versions of Cinderella from different cultures. When I taught second grade, we did a unit called 'Around the World With Cinderella.' Students made passports and read versions of Cinderella from several continents. They had to compare and contrast a few stories and then they wrote their own." - Kenya Brown

11. Flip the script

"After my second graders study fairy tales, we read The End by David LaRochelle. It starts with 'and they all lived happily ever after,' and it ends as you can imagine with 'once upon a time.' My students think it's so funny!" - April Ralph.

Literary fairy tales of moral, educational and educational significance, including works of art that are studied in Literature lessons in the absorption of beautiful qualities into the hearts of the youth of today, the owners of our future, are a source of genuine didactics.

Therefore, the correct Organization of literary fairy-tale lessons is another bold step towards the goal pursued by literary education.

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